
Full Length Research Paper

Effect of gender on students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach

Oluwatosin Victor Ajayi^{1*}, Terver Samuel Agamber² and Terfa Michael Angura¹

¹Department of Curriculum and Teaching, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

²Department of Biology, College of Education, Oju, Benue State, Nigeria.

Accepted 26 October, 2017

In this study, the effect of gender on students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach was investigated. A sample of 198 students from six purposively selected secondary schools out of a population of 3,706 Senior Secondary I students from Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria was used for the study. The study adopted non-equivalent quasi-experimental research design. The instrument used for data collection was Separation Techniques Interest Inventory (STII) with the reliability value of 0.84 using Kuder-Richardson (KR-21). Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance. The study revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean interest scores between male and female students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach; [$F(1,97) = 6.300, P > 0.050$]. It also found no significant interaction effect between methods and gender on the mean interest scores of students in standard mixture separation techniques; [$F(1,197) = 0.318, P > 0.050$]. It was recommended that both male and female students should be involved in ethnochemistry and chemistry curriculum should be restructured to reflect Nigerian culture (indigenous chemistry practices) in order to enhance both male and female students' interest.

Key words: Ethnochemistry, gender, interest, standard mixture separation techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Chemistry is the scientific study of the composition, structure, properties, and reactions of matter. The importance and value of chemistry in the social and economic sphere of any nation is immense and Nigeria is not an exception. Chemistry is a broad scientific subject and its relevance is seen in almost every aspect of society including medicine, food security and agriculture, science and technology, cooking, and environmental issues. Chemistry enables students to understand what

happens in the world they live in and how it contributes to the quality of life on our planet (Ware, 2001). Due to its importance, the teaching of chemistry should be done in such a manner that students would have deep understanding and interest for it. In this regard, if chemistry is properly taught using effective methods or approaches, chemistry could arouse students' interest and provide the nation with valuable development, which is required for the achievement of both personal and national goals. Interest is describes the qualities that arouse concern or curiosity that holds a child's attention on an object (Ayuba, 2015).

According to Adeyemi (2013), students' interest in

*Corresponding author. E-mail: drvictorajayi@gmail.com.

chemistry is jeopardized by the teachers' authoritarian and introverted methods to teaching. These methods such as lecture and discussion methods reduce chemistry to a series of stories written on the chalkboard that have little no meaning to the students. In this regard, the scholar advocates the use of innovative approaches as a way of getting students interested in chemistry. There is need therefore to teach chemistry in an inspiring manner in order to achieve meaningful learning. Interest is an important variable in learning because when one becomes interested in an activity one is likely to be deeply involved and inspired to learn. A recent research carried out by Olorundare (2014), to find out causes of poor achievement in senior secondary certificate examination in their chemistry examination shows that most of the students doing chemistry have very little or no interest in the subject.

The researcher further added that, for decades now, teachers, parents, government and the general public have been perplexed and disturbed immensely by the lack of students interest in chemistry. This is because chemistry introduced in our system is foreign and euro-centric in origin, and built on western cultural background and it has no meaning to students because it seems unreal. Therefore, they resorted to learning by rote memorization, which resulted in consistent poor achievement. A meta-analysis of the causes of students' lack of interest in chemistry by Ajayi (2017) suggested that lack of students' interest in chemistry may be attributed to the use of conventional teaching methods such as lecture, discussion and demonstration methods that does not consider the students' culture, environment, background, and experience in teaching and learning processes. However, there have been ongoing endeavours to explore and implement several possible interventions to improve students' interest in chemistry. One of such interventions is to teach the subject beginning from what the student already knows. This brings about meaningful learning (Gregory and Mayer, 2002). The inclusion of knowledge related to ethnochemistry practices may instill a sense of ownership about the concept and remove improve students interest' in chemistry. In this regard, ethnochemistry may help to sequence teaching/learning processes through previous knowledge of the culture, so as to offer the opportunity for learners to know more about reality, culture, society and themselves.

Ethno encompasses identifiable cultural groups such as national tribal societies, labour groups, ideologies, daily practices and specific way of reasoning and inferring. Indra and Bitwell (2016) opine that ethnochemistry are the various chemically related cultural and community practices. Ethnochemistry is the study of chemistry practices of specific cultural groups in the course of dealing with their environmental problems and activities using their own ideologies. In this regard, ethnochemistry teaching approach can be describe as a

means of organizing chemistry instruction based on diverse cultural context. Ethnochemistry approach to chemistry curriculum is an approach that draws on traditional culture while focusing attention on the chemistry needed by the learners in an integrated society. In other words, ethnochemistry teaching approach is an approach adopted by the teacher in the process of teaching chemistry through the use of learners' "culture" background, in understanding, explaining and managing situations and activities arising in their own environment.

In this regard, the aim of ethnochemistry approach in this study is to use already existing familiar mixture separation techniques activities in the learners' culture, environment, background, reasoning and experiences, integrated with foreign-centric standard mixture separation techniques to help them develop skills to improve their level of standard mixture separation techniques functioning in a wide range of standard mixture separation techniques with the goal of improving their interest in such concepts. According to Kurumeh and Opara (2008) ethno method of teaching involves situating learning and problem solving in real life contexts where the environment is very rich in information with physical materials that serve as a source of manipulative and interactive processes; Students are made to link the past to the present so as to build the future; The teacher then explores the cultural experiences of the learners based on the initial experiences to teach the present school (academic) and relate new learning to their environmental usefulness.

Many students and teachers experience chemistry as a rather strange subject, imported from outside Africa (Indra and Bitwell, 2016). In order to overcome this psychological and cultural blockage to the learning and development of chemistry, ethnochemistry practices may be incorporated into chemistry lessons in order to improve students' interest in chemistry. Incorporating ethnochemistry in chemistry instruction may enable students to see chemistry as a familiar subject, and not one that is strange and imported strange from outside Africa. Indeed, these indigenous chemically related practices may be used to make the unfamiliar chemistry content familiar to students. For instance, mixture separation phases of brine in traditional production of table salt (sodium chloride) may be used when teaching standard mixture separation techniques such as filtration, or decantation. Furthermore, the traditional practice of blacksmithing can be used when teaching extraction of iron in the blast furnace.

Standard mixture separation technique is a scientific process or method to achieve any phenomenon that converts a mixture of chemical substance into two or more distinct product mixtures, which may be referred to as mixture, at least one of which is enriched in one or more of the mixture's constituents (Wilson and Adlard, 2005). The scholars further explained that, in some

cases, a separation may fully divide the mixture into its pure constituents. Separations are carried out based on difference in chemical properties such as size, shape, mass, or chemical affinity between the constituents of a mixture, and are often classified according to the particular differences they use to achieve separation. Mustafa (2015) explains that, the method used to separate mixtures depends upon the type of mixture. The author further outlines types of standard mixture separation techniques such as extraction, filtration, decantation, evaporation, sublimation, simple and fractional distillation, crystallization, and chromatography among others. The study incorporated the ethnochemistry knowledge relevant to different types or methods of standard mixture separation technique concepts such as filtration, distillation, evaporation, extraction and sedimentation/decantation in chemistry lessons.

Gender inequality in science education has remained a perennial problem of global scope. The term gender is used to indicate the distinction between human beings based on masculinity and femininity in relation to their expected roles in the society. Gipps [10] defines gender as the expectation a society has formed about someone simply because the person is a man or woman. By implication, gender is ascribed to an attitude that differentiates feminine from masculine in interest due to gender inequality which has caused a lot of concern to educationalists. In this regard, the differences between boys and girls in relation to students' interest in chemistry have received a lot of attention in recent years. Some studies indicate that boys have higher interest than girls (Esan, 2004), either no difference (Tile, 2013; Ajayi, 2017) or girls have higher interest than boys (Bajah, 2007; Lakshmi, 2015; Ajiboye, 2015). Studies on gender differences in chemistry interest continue to yield inconsistent results and these have usually been attributed to unequal exposure of boys and girls to learning instructions relevant to chemistry learning. It is on this note, the study examined effect of gender on senior secondary chemistry students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approaches in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State as a study area. Specifically, the purpose of the study was to;

- i.) Determined the difference in effect of ethnochemistry approach between male and female students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques.
- ii.) Ascertained the interaction effect between methods and gender on students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- i. What is the difference in the mean interest scores between male and female students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach?
- ii. What is the interaction effect between methods and genders on students' mean interest scores in standard mixture separation techniques?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

- i.) There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores between male and female students taught Standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach.
- ii.) There is no significant interaction effect between methods and gender on the mean interest scores of students in standard mixture separation techniques.

Ethnochemistry and its practical application in standard mixture separation techniques

Viewed from all perspectives ethnochemistry is rooted from ethnosience. According to Atran 1991, ethnosience looks at culture with a scientific perspective. The scholar further added that ethnosience refers to knowledge that is indigenous to a particular culture. Ethnosience is concerned with natural objects and events that may have potentially the same branches as the western science, therefore, one may speak of ethnophysics, ethnobiology, ethnochemistry, ethnozology, ethnomedicine and so on. As earlier remarked, an ethnochemistry teaching approach is described as means of organizing chemistry instruction based on diverse cultural contexts. In the present study, traditional or ethno knowledge of salt making processes relevant to standard mixture separation techniques concepts such as extraction, filtration, sedimentation, decantation and evaporation in chemistry lessons are particularly employed in Ebonyi State as it is the second largest small-scale salt producing area in Nigeria. Small-scale salt production in Uburu and Okposi Okwu districts in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State has continued for over 40 decades.

Uburu district consists of fourteen villiages namely; Amaenu, Amegu, Ihenu, Mgbom, Obiozara, Ogwu, Ubuaba, Umuagwu-Oke, Umuanketa, Umuantum, Umuchima, Umuobuma, Umuodu-Igbo and Urobo. Okoposi district consist of ten villiages namely; Amechi, AmeluAgu, Amenu, Anaeko/Mebiokpa, Mebiowa, Mgbom/Achara, Okposi Okwu, Umuekma, Umuka, and Umunuka. Ugwu-Langwu district consist of ten villiages namely; Amaegudu, Amelu, Amenu, Anata, Mgbom, Ohachara, Ufuezeraku, Ufuovoke, Umuifere, and Umuigboke. Akaeze district consist of four villiages

namely; Akaeze Ukwu, Ihenta, Lijioji, and Umuobor, while, Ishiagu district consist of sixteen villiages namely; Afikpo road, Amaeke, Amaeze, Amagu, Amaokwe, Amata, Eziato, Ihiali, Ihie, Ihietutu, Nguogwo, Nzerem, Obinagu, Ogor and Okue

Uburu and Okposi Okwu people in Ebonyi State are very rich in culture and tradition. The traditional occupation of the Uburu and Okposi Okwu people is salt production. Salt or table salt, is a crystalline mineral that is primarily composed sodium chloride (NaCl). It is essential for animal life in small quantities, but is harmful to animals and plants in excess. Salt is one of the oldest, most ubiquitous food seasonings and salting is an important method of food preservation. Like all other people in the world, Uburu and Okposi Okwu people have their indigenous and native process or method with which they carry out their day to day salt production activities. Meanwhile, scientifically, salt making process from brine involves a series of mixture separation phrases.

As earlier remarked, the main occupation of Uburu and Okposi Okwu people is salt production. Therefore, their traditional mixture separation technique practices evolved in their quest to produce salt from the brine (Brine is water containing a high concentration of salt). The people of Ebonyi State of Nigeria especially Uburu and Okposi Okwu people in Ohaozara Local Government Area mainly have very rich cultural practices that could be used to advantage to teach standard mixture separation techniques in Chemistry. Consequently, how they produce their salt is interesting. Meanwhile, note that no matter how crude the method, salt preparation is not a craft but a scientific process. In this regard, the making process from brine scientifically involves series of standard mixture separation phrases such as extraction, filtration, decantation, evaporation, sublimation, among other phases.

Let us consider their traditional salt production process. The people especially women begin salt production by securing a piece of land (salt plot) and leveling it, after which they provide big earthen pots which may be six or more depending on their ability. The pots are arranged in a straight line and supported with big stones, which raise the pots completely from the ground. With wet clay soil, the stones are held together and in place. These large pots in a line are called by Uburu people "Ofufu" (Ofufu is a pot perforated at a base) behind the "Ofufu" is mounted another pot larger than Ofufu. The larger pot is called "Onini" which has different function from "Ofufu". The larger pot behind the Ofufu is meant for storing brine to be used in Ofufu when necessary.

The actual salt production starts with the collection of 'salty earth' from the water-bed of the lake using a flat metal called "atakpa" (that process is extraction: a separation technique used to separate a desired substance from a natural source). Thereafter, the big pots (ofufu) are filled with earth until it gets to the brim. The

water and the earth in the big pots (ofufu) are allowed to knead properly by leaving them over night with the small perforations at the bottom of the Ofufu which is still blocked. In the morning, the perforations at the bottom of the Ofufu are opened (irufu eja) to allow the filtrate to drain into the earthen conical dish beneath the "Ofufu-nja ugbani" (that process is extraction: a separation technique used to separate heterogeneous mixtures composed of solids and liquids. The technique uses a porous barrier to separate the solid from the liquid). Sometimes they use "alum" to affect sedimentation of dirt before pouring off the upper liquid layer (that process is decantation is a separation technique used to separate a liquid from an insoluble solid). Then the filtrate in the "nja ugbani" is collected and taken home for boiling to get salt (that process is evaporation: In this separation method, the mixture is heated, when the mixture has completely evaporated, no water is left behind. The solid salt left behind is the residue).

Research design and procedure

The study used pre-test, post-test non-equivalent quasi experimental design. The design was considered appropriate because intact classes were used. The study area was Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 3,706 SSI students in the 37 government approved secondary schools. One hundred and five (105) male and 93 female students were purposively sampled from 6 schools that had some basic facilities and equipment in their laboratories. The experimental group was taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry in line with lessons procedures prepared by the researcher while the control group was taught standard mixture separation techniques using the discussion lesson notes.

An instrument known as Separation Techniques Interest Inventory (STII) was developed by the researchers and validated by three experts from the science education unit and one expert from the measurement and evaluation unit from Benue State University, Makurdi was used to collect the data. STII contained two sections. Section "A" contained demographic information of the respondents, while section "B" contained a 30-item questionnaire that as intended to help students express their interest toward standard mixture separation techniques. Each of the items is a 5-point Likert-rating scale with 5 response options. The options are Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). STII was administered twice as pre-test and post-test though reshuffled. The reason for Pre-STII and Post-STII was to ascertain students' interest before and after treatment. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) was used to obtain the STII reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of

Table 1. Mean interest and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach.

Ethnochemistry Group	N	PRE-STII		POST-STII		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	51	12.10	1.40	30.07	6.77	17.97
Female	47	12.19	1.34	31.18	5.91	18.99
Mean difference		0.09		1.11		1.02

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation scores of interaction effect between methods and gender on students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques.

Gender	Approach	N	POST-STII	
			Mean	SD
Male	Ethnochemistry	51	30.07	6.77
	Discussion	54	21.29	4.99
Female	Ethnochemistry	47	31.18	5.91
	Discussion	46	20.47	4.73

0.84. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance

RESULTS

Research question one

What is the difference in the mean interest scores between male and female students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach? The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1.

Table 1 revealed that the mean interest difference of both gender as 1.02. This difference, though small is in favour of the female students. This implies that female students gained slightly higher interest than their male counterparts in standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach.

Research question two

What is the interaction effect between methods and gender on students mean interest scores in standard mixture separation techniques? The answer to research question two is presented in Table 2.

The results in Table 2 revealed that, the mean interest scores of male students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach than discussion method are 30.07 and 21.29 respectively while the mean interest scores of female students taught

standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and discussion method are 31.18 and 20.47 respectively. This shows that ethnochemistry teaching approach is superior to discussion method in enhancing both male and female students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores between male and female students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach. The answer to hypothesis one is presented in Table 3.

ANCOVA Test results in Table 3 reveal that there is no significant difference between the mean interest of male and female students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach ($F(1,97) = 6.300, P > 0.050$). The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that ethnochemistry enhanced both male and female students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant interaction effect between methods and gender on the mean interest scores of students in standard mixture separation techniques. The answer to hypothesis two is presented in Table 4.

ANCOVA results in Table 4 revealed that the interaction effect between methods and gender on the mean interest scores of students in standard mixture separation techniques is not significant ($F(1,197) = 0.318,$

Table 3. ANCOVA test for mean interest scores of male and female students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach.

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	2914.807a	2	987.017	222.008	0.000
Intercept	2035.005	1	2035.005	260.095	0.000
Pre-test	211.098	1	211.098	67.876	0.000
Gender	55.003	1	55.003	6.300	0.221
Error	728.144	95	11.021		
Total	80003.060	98			
Corrected Total	572.578	97			

a. R squared = .827 (Adjusted R Squared= .815).

Table 4. ANCOVA tests for interaction effect between methods and gender on students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques.

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	1061.191a	2	429.977	72.105	.000
Intercept	1921.171	1	1921.171	43.015	.000
Pre-test	201.001	1	201.001	87.007	.000
Methods*Gender	.122	1	.122	.318	.511
Error	642.001	195	10.111		
Total	539004.100	198			
Corrected Total	2806.280	197			

a. R squared = .409 (Adjusted R Squared= .517).

$P > 0.050$). The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no need for separation of instructional method for male and female students since ethnochemistry teaching approach can successfully be used to enhance the interest of the two groups.

Discussion of findings

The study examined the effect of gender on senior secondary I chemistry students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach. The findings of this study revealed that female students gained slightly higher interest scores than their male counterparts using ethnochemistry approach. The likely explanation for this slight difference may be connected to the fact that traditional salt making process in the study area is usually carried out by the female. Meanwhile, ANCOVA test shows that the difference was not significant. Generally speaking, the likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that ethnochemistry teaching approach helped the learners to integrate or link their cultural background of the study and their immediate environment with the scientific way of learning standard mixture separation techniques when compared to discussion method. This finding is in agreement with Achor et al. (2009) who reported that students exposed to ethnomathematics teaching approach were superior in achievement and retention compared to those exposed to conventional

teaching methods. In the same vein, the finding is also in agreement with Ajayi and Ogbeba (2017) who found no gender disparity in students' achievement in stoichiometry using hands-on activities. However, this finding contradicts the finding of Ajiboye [5] who found gender disparity in students' interest in favour of females in basic science and technology. Based on this finding, interest in standard mixture separation techniques is therefore not dependent on gender. This means that the age long disparity in chemistry specifically in standard mixture separation techniques between male and female students can be laid to rest with the use of ethnochemistry teaching approach. The finding of this study also revealed that there is no significant interaction effect between methods and gender on mean interest scores of students in standard mixture separation techniques. It shows that ethnochemistry teaching approach is superior to the discussion method irrespective of gender in fostering students' interest. In this case, there is no need for separation of instructional method for males and females since ethnochemistry approach can be used successfully for the two groups.

Conclusion

No gender disparity exists in the interest of male and female chemistry students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach. This implies that incorporating ethnochemistry

practices in teaching chemistry significantly enhanced secondary school students' interest towards standard mixture separation technique. Therefore, ethnochemistry approach is very rewarding for students' in-terms of interest regardless of their gender.

Recommendations

i.) Ethnochemistry teaching approach is not gender sensitive; therefore, both male and female students should be involved in ethnochemistry to enhance their interest in chemistry concepts specifically standard mixture separation techniques.

ii.) Ministry of Education and professional bodies such as the Association of Science Educators (ASE), Teacher Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organise conferences or seminars and workshops to popularize and sensitize chemistry teachers on the integration of ethnochemistry knowledge in teaching standard mixture separation techniques and chemistry curriculum should be restructured to reflect Nigerian culture (indigenous chemistry practices) in order to enhance both male and female students' interest.

REFERENCES

- Achor EE, Imoko BI, Uloko ES (2009). Effect of ethnomathematics teaching approach on senior secondary students' achievement and retention in Locus. *Edu. Res. and Rev.*, 4(8): 385-390.
- Adeyemi A (2013). Attitudes towards chemistry: A quantitative synthesis. *Sci. Edu*, 108 (12), 147-167.
- Ajayi OV (2017). Effect of hands-on activity-based method on interest of senior secondary students in organic chemistry. *Scholarly J. of Edu.*, 6(1): 1-5.
- Ajayi OV, Ogbaba J.(2017). Effect of gender on senior secondary chemistry students' achievement in stoichiometry using hands-on activities. *Am. J. Edu. Res.*, 5(8): 839-842
- Ajiboye MM (2015). Effects of two methods of teaching on students' interest in basic science and technology. *Greener J. of Edu. Res.*, 3(3): 12-18
- Atran S (1991). Cultural mosaics and mental models of nature. *Proceedings of the National Academic of Science*, 104 (35): 13868-13874.
- Ayuba A (2015). Effect of inquiry approach on students' achievement and interest in Integrated Science among junior secondary students in Akwanga local Government Area of Nasarawa State. Unpublished M.Ed dissertation, Nassarawa State University, Keffi.
- Bajah KK (2007). Influence of gender and ability on senior secondary school students achievement on the concept of culture and the society. *Int. J. of Educ.*, 34: 234-256.
- Esan JN (2012). Achievement, interest and gender in Science Education. *J. of Res. in Edu. Rev.*, 2(5), 43-48.
- Gipps KS (2004). Gender Inequality. In Therney, H. (Ed.) *Women's Studies Encyclopedia*. New York: Peter Bedrick Books
- Gregory JK, Mayer ER (2002). Meaningful Learning: The Essential Factor for Conceptual Change in Limited or Inappropriate Propositional Hierarchies Leading to Empowerment of Learners (eds). Florida: Cornell University.
- Indra SS, Bitwell C (2016). Effect of ethnochemistry practices on secondary school students' attitude towards chemistry. *J. of Educ and Practice*, 7(17): 44-56.
- Kurumeh MS, Opara MF (2008). Innovative Teaching Approaches of Mathematics Education in the 21st century. Makurdi: Azaben Publishers.
- Lakshmi A (2015). Gender and interest in physics using problem solving. *IHU Teachers J.*, 2(5): 12-17.
- Mustafa S (2015). Standard mixture separation techniques. Retrieved on 2nd June, 2016 from http://www.separation_techniques_by_dr_sana_mustafa.pdf
- Olorundare AS (2014). Correlates of poor academic performance of secondary school students in the Science in Nigeria. Paper presented at the international institute for capacity Building in Higher Education, Virginia State University, Virginia, USA. 20th-31st June, 2014
- Tile MT (2013). Effect of activity-based on psychomotor skills acquisition and interest of senior secondary 2 in Biology. Unpublished M.Ed Dissertation. Benue State University, Makurdi
- Ware SA (2001). Teaching Chemistry from Societal Perspective. *Pure and Applied Chemistry* 3(7): 1209-1214.
- Wilson LD, Adlard ER (2005). *Encyclopedia of separation science*. San Diego: Academic Press.

Citation: Ajayi, OV., Agamber , ST, Angura, TM. (2017). Effect of gender on students' interest in standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry teaching approach. *Sky.J.Edu.Res*, 5(5),27-33
